

Gender Discrimination in Shashi Deshpande's *The Dark Holds No Terror*

Dr. D. Saraswathi, Assistant Professor of English, Sri.S.R.N.M College, Sattur, Tamil Nadu, India.

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4049-2532>

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7809910

Abstract

Gender is a universal term used in the space of identification and where Gender discrimination is destined just for women because women are the only targeted victims of gender discrimination in a patriarchal society. In India, mostly women at a young age depending on their father, in the middle age-she depend on their husband, and in the older age-depend on their son. Women always depend on somebody for their livelihoods. Hence, independence in economical aspects is imperative for women's development. The novel "The Dark Hold No Terror" elicits the sufferings of working woman who has become a puppet in a male chauvinistic society. Shashi Deshpande portrays her women characters as the victims of the male-oriented modern society. In this novel, Sarita (Saru) is the female protagonist who narrates the story of her tale. By the narration, one can know her parents, late brother Dhurva, her husband Manohar, and her old teacher Boozie. It gives out the reminiscences of the protagonist. She is futile of her state and decides not to dispute the domination by breaching her familial life.

Keywords: Gender Discrimination, Shashi Deshpande, *The Dark Holds No Terror*.

Gender discrimination is a violent act against an individual or a group on the grounds of sex or gender identity. The word 'gender discrimination' justifies the deed of unjust maltreatment of an individual or group based on personal or group prejudice. Socially, the sexual difference has been used to justify cultures in which one sex or the other has been restricted to considerably inferior and secondary roles. We know that gender is a universal term. Gender discrimination is used to mention only women because females are the only victims of gender inequity. She is not only biologically but also socially determined. Proper and perpetuate efforts are taken to avoid these prejudices. Women are discriminated against based on denial of equality, rights and opportunity and suppression in any form based on gender. Half of the world's population is female. Two-thirds of work of the total work in the world is done by females but received only one-tenth of the world's total income. Two-thirds of the women are illiterates but they have possessed only one per cent of the total world's assets. It is known that India is a patriarchal society and all possible gender discrimination is habitually done against women.

Berta Esteve-volart (2004) described that gender bigotry against women in the world reduces the available talent in an economy It has negative economic consequences. It has many social practices seen as normal from a religious or cultural point of view that have women out of the economic mainstream. Such evil social practices have reflective economic consequences on the country and the families. They do not allow society to take advantage of the talent inherent in women. Male dominance is the origin of gender-based discrimination. In India, a woman still needs the anchor of a husband and a family. The male domination nature has led women to walk with their heads down. It was all practised from the beginning and is followed to date. In parliament, the opposing parties believe that women are born to do

household tasks and manage children and families. A woman at a young age depends on her father, in the middle age-she depends on her husband and in the older age-depends on her son. There is always dependence on somebody for her livelihood. Hence, there is a need for independence in economical aspects for the development of women. The decision-making power of women is denied in the family as well as in society. As a rule, man makes important decisions in the family and society. This makes women voiceless and destroys their self-confidence and she feels less important in the family as well as in society. Consequently, to stop gender discrimination women have to empower themselves in decision-making situations. Similar to men, women must play important roles in the family and the nation. But her contribution is not recognized by the male-dominated society.

Shashi Deshpande is an award-winning novelist. Her novels usually have a woman as the protagonist. It had made her readers call her a feminist writer and critic. She is considered one of the most accomplished contemporary Indian women writers in English. Deshpande is exceptional with an instinctive literary mind which portrayed the characters with her experiences of life. Shashi Deshpande is known for creating. The women characters in Deshpande's women protagonists are a victim of the prevalent gross gender discrimination - first as a daughter and later as wives. The novel *The Dark Hold No Terrors* throws light on the struggles of a middle-class working woman who has become a trap in a male-dominated society. There is a clear picture of her men and women characters as the victim of modern society. Sarita (Saru) who is the female protagonist narrates the story. Her narration portrays the characters like her parents, her dead brother Dhurva, her husband Manohar (manu) and Boozie, (old teacher). She is not ready to protest against the oppression quality openly by breaking her familial life.

The first half of *The Dark Hold No Terrors* deals with the unkind, vicious and prejudiced of Saru's mother. She is a strong product of patriarchy for her son's death. "why didn't you die? Why are you alive and he dead". (P.[14]) Saru undergoes gender discrimination at home even in her childhood. Her mother's attitude is typical of most Indian mothers and Saru's problem is increased when the younger brother accidentally dies by drowning. It becomes the turning point of her life. Saru's mother's obvious preference for her brother, Dhruva, creates a sense of alienation within Saru. It produces a sense of insecurity.

I didn't truly, I didn't, It was an accident. I loved him, my little brother. I tried to save him. Truly I tried, but I couldn't. And I ran way yes, I ran way, I admit that but I didn't kill him (P. 146)

This difference in her mother's treatment of her son and daughter enrages Saru. Being a traditional Hindu woman, the mother considers. She must remind her daughter that she is grown up and she should behave accordingly. It is a mother's responsibility to see that the children especially the daughters behave well. When Saru attains menarche, their first experience of menstruation is horrifying and painful to her. Instead of explaining the process to her and putting her at ease, the mother makes her fear the fact that she would bleed for years. She is not allowed to enter the kitchen and puja room. She is compelled to sleep on a straw mat separate plate and a tumbler is provided to her, which makes her feel like an outcast during those days. It is a great wonder for Saru why women are considered unholy during the menstruation period. She feels like an unwanted child who is perplexed at her very being.

Saru, the Indian girl-child is puzzled and panicky at the physical changes taking place within her body at the time of puberty. She feels repugnant and hideous. She is not happy

with the growth of her body. She is warned that she is stepping into that difficult and shameful state of womanhood. Time and again Saru is made to realize that with physical growth, she has been vulnerable to the atrocious and ravenous clutches of society. Time and again she is made to realize that being the girl she is different and not as privileged as a boy indicating gender discrimination. It takes time for young, Saru to understand she was a female and some things are bound to happen.

Things fell, with a miraculous exactness, into place. I was a female. I was born that way, that was the way my body had to be, those were the things that had to happen to me. And that was that (P.63)

She rebels against her mother “if you are a woman, I don’t want to be one” (P.55), says Saru to her mother. The words of Saru reveal to us her hatred for the life of a woman and the basis of discrimination meted out to women at large because of the patriarchal system. Saru’s first public defiance of the patriarchal power system is when she breaks the so-called protective barrier of her house and leaves home. With a deep-seated hurt feeling, she says to her mother, “you don’t want me to have anything; you don’t want me to do anything. You don’t even want me to live” (P.142). Bitterness and hatred for her mother drive her to leave home and obsessively seek success in medical college.

The whole novel is full of occurrences showing gender-based discrimination against women. Sarita’s mother shows detestation and bitterness towards her daughter and thinks that she too should have died when her son died. Sarita is not even recognized as a daughter. The mother remarks: “...Daughter? I don’t have any daughter. I had a son and he died. Now I am childless” (P.196). Sarita’s brother, Dhruva’s disappearance in the pond and her father’s punishing the mother by not eating food cooked by her reminds Sarita of a Sanskrit story from her school text where a woman did not disturb her husband’s sleep even to save her child from a fire. Agni, the god of fire, had to come and save the child. It suggests that a woman was made to be the handmaid of a man, whose work is only to wait on a man. Gender discrimination is vividly displayed here. Saru wants to be recognized as a person than as a woman and she wants to have an independent social image. It makes Sarita extremely angry at gender discrimination and she thinks,

...who wrote that story? A man, of course. Telling all women for all time your duty to me comes first. And women poor feels, believed him. So even today Dhruva's mother considers it a punishment to be deprived of a chance to serve her husband.” (P.207).

The second half deals with the life of Saru as a wife. Saru undergoes gender discrimination as a wife too. She suffers the sexual torture of her husband, Manohar, (Manu) who thinks that being a male he has all right to treat his wife as he wants. Saru’s introspection at her father’s home brings an answer to her question by her and for that, she needs to voice her felling. Manohar (Saru’s husband) is solely an Indian man. He is an underpaid college teacher. In the beginning, their life was normal. In one of the interviews, a female journalist asks Manu how does it feel when his wife earns not only butter but most of the bread as well? At that time he laughed with Saru. He makes fun of her. So, he feels pride manifest in the form of sexual sadism. Manu and Saru planned for a tour to Ooty. At the time of shopping, they meet up with Manu’s colleague and his wife. He doesn’t behave like a husband in privacy at night but acted like a rapist. In this novel, women characters dominate the men characters. So, Deshpande tries to bring justice to her female characters. The female character shares a lot about their suffering, their inner trauma, and victim of marital rape, the silence of the male character conveys their dilemma, suffering inferiority and male adjustment.

As a consequence of the treatment meted at home and in a bid to search for her identity, Saru resolves to be a doctor, hoping that a professional career could be the key that would unlock the door out of the wretched life at home. Whether it is her profession or marriage, Sarita had to put up with the opposition of her mother. Her defiance is expressed when she becomes economically independent and marries a man of her own choice. “women, to achieve freedom, seek marriage as an alternative to the bondage created by the parental family. Saru resents the role of a daughter and looks forward to the role of wife, with the hope that her new role will help in winning freedom”.

She hopes that the role of a wife will give her relief from the oppression of the mother, and will give her freedom from this gender discrimination which she was not able to understand or tolerate. Her married life with Manu had its ups and downs and it makes her think that even pleasure is a fantasy whereas grief seems more real having mass and mother. The departure of Saru from her mother makes her step into autonomy. Manu cannot tolerate people greeting her and ignoring him. Gender-based discrimination continues even in the professional arena. Saru being a lady doctor is preferred by all. She gets respect and her husband can't digest that. These qualities made the loving husband into an utter sadist. Saru feels a gradual disappearance of the love which she had once developed for Manu. She starts hating the man-woman relationship which is based on attraction and need, not love.

Manu's sexual overtures hurt the woman in Saru. She cannot free herself from him as she lives in a concrete society. Moreover, the next morning after the night's ordeal, he used be the same smiling Manu again which Saru is not able to understand or digest. As a man, Manu had the liberty to treat his wife the way he wanted, even to the brink of marital rape. But Saru being a woman could not stop his overtures or even complain about it.

The hurting hands, the savage teeth the monstrous assault of a horrible familiar's body. And above me a face I could not recognize”. (P.112)

Deshpande investigates the tension and sufferings of being a woman in a patriarchal society. She concentrates keenly on a woman's quest to find her true value. It doesn't take long for Saru to realize that her coming to her parental home after she gets to know about her mother's death and to seek refuge from her husband. It became a futile one and being a daughter she is expected to be happy with her husband. At the end of the novel when Saru is informed about Manu's arrival at her paternal home to take her back she is disturbed initially as she is upset about her relationship and does not want to take him. The moment she realizes the importance of life, she resolves to take charge of her life.

Deshpande draws the role of women and men of middle-class families where the female protagonists are highly qualified, courageous and strong in the male-dominated society. The realization that Saru gets after nearly a fortnight's stay in her father's house is that it is her life that she is living and she has to have all the hurdles herself. She has to live for her happiness by forgetting all about the past. “it is my life and I have the right to live in my way”. She gets the courage to face the dark. The dark wherein she was subjugated to physical and mental torture by her husband. She knows that *The Dark Hold No Terrors* if she rises to face it. The positive note in the climax of the novel matured Saru. She will do everything possible not to let gender discrimination come in the way of her happiness. She will fight it out and makes her life better.

References

- [1] Deshpande, Shashi. *The Dark Holds No Terror*. Penguin Books, New Delhi. 1980.

- [2] Beauvoir, Simone De. *The Second Sex*. translated and edited by H.M.Parshily, Placodon Classics Edition published 1988 by Pan Books Ltd. Cavage Place London.
- [3] Singh Jyoti. *Indian Women Novelists: Feminist Physiological Study*. Jaipur: Rawat Publications, 2007.

Author Contribution Statement: NIL.

Author Acknowledgement: NIL.

Author Declaration: I declare that there is no competing interest in the content and authorship of this scholarly work.

The content of the article is licensed under <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/> International License.